

Efficient 6D Object Pose Estimation for Robotic Grasping using Lightweight Neural Network Architectures

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Abstract. We present the implementation of a simple and lightweight model for 6D object pose estimation for robotic grasping tasks. Our approach has obtained great results on several industrial scenarios. Lightweightness is achieved through the use of neural network backbones inside our architecture. These backbones have great performance for feature extraction, which we exploit to achieve our results. Our approach uses a 6 dimensional space to represent rotation, providing benefits to conventional approaches like Euler angles and quaternions.

Keywords: computer vision, pose estimation, neural networks, robotics

1 Introduction

Groundbreaking robotic tasks are expected to deftly manipulate multiple known objects in a given environment. This requires robust and accurate vision systems capable of identifying and estimating the position and orientation of objects of interest. In the field of computer vision, this is referred to as 6D pose estimation: the 3D position being x , y , and z , while the 3D orientation consists of roll, pitch, and yaw angles. This task has garnered attention in robotics and augmented reality, among other activities, due to the need to manipulate and interact with objects in related scenarios.

Ideal 6D pose estimation solutions should be lightweight, fast, easy to adapt, and easy to use. However, most of the existing approaches either require powerful systems capable of intensive computing or are complicated to adapt outside of their given pipeline. In this research, we focus exclusively on the 6D pose estimation task, given that the known object is previously segmented. We propose a lightweight model capable of performing fast and accurate pose estimation. We introduce a stand alone solution and a training pipeline that is easy to adapt to a wide range of robotic applications.

2 Related Work

Many methodologies have emerged for 6D pose estimation, each with different results regarding speed, accuracy, and robustness to real-world conditions. Early

methodologies for object pose estimation used extracted keypoints from the object and image for geometric calculations. The most prominent algorithms born from this approach are the Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) [8] and the Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF) [1]. However, these methods struggle with textureless surfaces where keypoint extraction is challenging. Another approach is based on generating pre-rendered views of the object from different angles to compare against a real image and perform the estimation. Hinterstoisser *et al.* [5] introduced a key contribution, where color gradients and surface normals are used to detect and estimate the 6D pose of an object. Recent advancements in AI have also been beneficial to object pose estimation. One of the most notable contributions to 6D pose estimation is PoseCNN [11], which introduced a convolutional neural network architecture to estimate the position and orientation of an object. On the other hand, Deep6DPose [3] leveraged deep learning with a pipeline to extract keypoints of an object and estimate its pose. One of the more widespread breakthroughs came with the Deep Object Pose Estimation (DOPE) [9] model, which performs object detection and pose estimation with a CAD-based keypoint regression. Most recently, FoundationPose [10] has achieved state of the art results on 6D pose estimation while proposing two operation methods: model-based and model-free.

2.1 Benchmarks and Datasets

The effectiveness of these methods can be evaluated through several public datasets. The LineMOD dataset [6], which includes RGB-D data with ground truth pose annotations, has been widely used to compare methods. Similarly, the YCB-Video dataset [11], introduced by Xiang *et al.* alongside PoseCNN, is used to assess pose estimation in cluttered, real-world scenes. It is important to mention the Benchmark for 6D Object Pose Estimation (BOP) [7], which unifies several public datasets under a single format, including LineMOD.

Concluding this section, the main remaining challenges on this task are related to reliance on large training data and real-time performance on modest setups. Our method proposes a lightweight model able to run in real-time and capable of working alongside a classical approach to provide accurate pose estimation.

3 Method

Our method leverages the performance of off-the-shelf neural network models and includes them as part of our architecture to perform feature extraction. We propose the use of segmented uncropped RGB images and X, Y, and Z maps as input to our model in the following dimensions: $[6, H, W]$, where H is the height of the matrix and W , the width. The input is processed by two branches: one dedicated to translation, while the other one estimates rotation. The translation branch takes the input through a ResNet-50 [4] block. The output of this ResNet is extracted out of the last convolutional block and processed with a series of

convolutional and upsampling layers, as observed in [11], to infer translation as a three dimensional vector. The rotation branch is an additional ResNet-50 block modified to infer a six dimensions rotation vector from our input.

This architecture provides a coarse pose estimation. This is refined with an ICP [12] algorithm, the reference CAD model, and the point cloud of the scene.

3.1 Experiment setup

Our model was tested both on the synthetic data generated in-house and with data acquired from a Photoneo MotionCam-3D color camera.

(a) In-house data

(b) Photoneo pointcloud

Fig. 1: Example of data acquired.

For each experiment the model was trained from start. No pretraining was loaded for any part of the model. All training and testing was executed on a computer with an Intel Xeon Silver 4280 CPU, an NVIDIA Quadro RTX 8000, and an NVME SSD.

3.2 Data Generation & Training

Since the main goal of this task is to be deployed in several industrial scenarios, it was required to generate relevant data to train and test our proposal. Synthetic data was generated with Blender [2] and real data was captured with a Photoneo MotionCAM-3D color camera. Our Photoneo’s camera matrix was used for data generation to ensure the synthetic data was generated as similar as possible to the captured data. Additionally, small variations to the color and texture were added to the CAD models to resemble the existent noise in real manufacturing processes. Light conditions, object position, object rotation, and object quantity were also randomized in the data generation pipeline.

For each object of interest, 1000 frames were processed. Each data generation was performed individually, meaning the images only contain one type of object. The output for every frame follows the format of the BOP dataset. For each experiment, the model was trained for 200 epochs. Every 50 epochs the learning rate was reduced to 10% of the previous value. The results shown in the following sections are the average of 5 repetitions.

4 Metrics & Results

The Average Distance of Model Points (ADD) [6] was used to evaluate the performance of our algorithm, which is the average distance between points of the ground truth model pose and the estimated pose. An estimated pose is correct if the ADD of that instance is above the average distance threshold. To compare results across multiple objects, the initial threshold was set at 10% of the model diameter. However, results are also shown for 5% and 2.5%.

$$ADD = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{x \in M} \|(Rx + t) - (\hat{R}x + \hat{t})\| \quad (1)$$

In equation 1, R and t refer to the ground truth pose, while \hat{R} and \hat{t} refer to the estimated pose.

In this section, we also present the results achieved by the experiments performed on our dataset. To validate the performance of our pipeline, we measured against three different thresholds for ADD: 0.1, 0.05, and 0.025.

	threshold = 0.1			threshold = 0.05			threshold = 0.025		
	OT (mm)	Ours (ADD)	Ours* (ADD)	OT (mm)	Ours (ADD)	Ours* (ADD)	OT (mm)	Ours (ADD)	Ours* (ADD)
Use Case A									
Brake Disc	37.27	66.40	80.97	18.64	66.40	80.97	9.32	66.40	80.97
Brake Plate	38.26	41.10	93.22	19.13	8.05	93.22	9.56	1.27	81.78
Caliper	24.79	71.63	100.00	12.39	31.52	99.14	6.20	6.59	91.40
Drum	38.38	58.85	88.94	19.19	21.68	88.50	9.59	0.88	86.73
Heat Cover	39.83	46.93	99.56	19.92	18.86	99.12	9.96	5.26	64.91
Hub	17.63	52.02	97.98	8.81	21.68	97.40	4.41	5.49	97.11
Spindle	17.69	71.51	98.92	8.84	34.92	98.92	4.42	7.39	98.92
Use Case B									
Chest Panel	7.62	13.60	90.93	3.81	1.42	81.87	1.90	0.00	64.02
Front Panel	14.81	22.31	98.16	7.40	6.04	88.71	3.70	0.79	81.89

Table 1: Evaluation of 6D pose estimation using ADD on our dataset, for three different thresholds. **OT** refers to the object-specific threshold. **Ours** refers to the result of our model. **Ours*** refers to the result of applying 20 ICP iterations on top of the initial pose estimated by our model.

The average performance of our model for all objects under a threshold of 0.1 is 49.37%, as observed in Table 1. Despite these not being groundbreaking results, the initial pose estimation is good enough to serve as initialization to apply ICP. After using ICP on the initial pose estimation, the performance rises consistently to an average of 94.29%. This result is mimicked, although with understandable lower performance, for 0.05 and 0.025 thresholds.

4.1 Inference speed

The complete pipeline for our implementation consists of the inference performed by the model and the finetuning with the ICP algorithm. Our model was tested several times on batches sizes ranging from 1 up to 20. The average speed of our model for one batch is 20ms. If we take into account the number of poses estimated per inference, it takes as little as 1ms per object when the batch size is 20, with potential to reduce even further if there are more objects to process in the same batch.

4.2 Validation

This section shows the result of using our model to infer the pose of a segmented object acquired by a Photoneo MotionCAM-3D. The reference sample data used for the following results is the same as shown in Figure 1b. Figure 2a shows the initial pose guess of our model, while Figure 2b shows the refined pose after 20 iterations of ICP. Figure 2c shows the model with both poses side by side. While

Fig. 2: Samples of results with real data. Image (a) shows the initial pose estimation of our model, while image (b) is the result after applying ICP to (a).

the change in the position of the object barely perceptible, the ICP fixes some slight inclination in the initial pose. Although the correction does not seem too big from the initial perspective, it could mean the difference between a correct and incorrect grasping in applications where precision is required.

The application of ICP shows a decrease in points farther away from the reference cloud. Using only the initial points, 85% of the points were below 10mm away to the reference. After applying ICP, this increased to 89%.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, we present our own convolutional network model, based on off-the-shelf backbones and proven methods to perform 6D pose estimation for several industrial objects. Our architecture performs the estimation of the rotation over

a 6 dimensional space, which allows it to avoid spatial discontinuities present in Euler angles and quaternion representations. Our work provides a strong first step to continue research down this line to bring accessibility and ease of implementation to 6D pose estimation. In future work we plan to test the generalization of this approach.

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